

Health care consolidation, travel time and emergency admissions: Evidence from Italy

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ABSTRACT

Objective: A goal of most universal healthcare systems is to ensure geographical access to its services for all (insured) citizens in need. The focus of our analysis is to evaluate the impact of the changes in geographical distance (proxied by travel time in minutes) from the commune of residence of the patient to the commune of the nearest acute hospital on AMI mortality and readmission rate in Italy.

Methods: We exploit the individual variation in hospital distance resulting from closing of emergency care hospitals. The data used in the study comes from hospital discharge data consisting of all AMI hospitalisations in Italy from 2010-2016. In a first step, we define the home hospital as the closest acute hospital from the commune of residence. In case of ties between two hospital, we choose the hospital with the highest number of AMI admissions. A hospital is said to be closed if the number of AMI admissions drops to 10 or below compared to the previous year. We look at all hospital closures from 2010 to 2016 and see how they affected the hypothetical travel time by care (TT) of citizens to their nearest (acute) hospital. In particular, we look at the population-weighted average of the shortest TT from each commune of residence to the commune of the nearest acute hospital. Our empirical analysis involves a panel data analysis with hospital and year fixed effects to control for time-invariant hospital heterogeneities and common time trends. Moreover, the observed individual level heterogeneity can be controlled using a rich set of covariates including a variable indicating the total number of acute hospitals in a defined radius around the commune of residence of the patient. To account for sample selection from out-of-hospital mortality, we control for comorbidity and death during transportation to the hospital or at home. For the former, we will utilize hospitalisations of the sampled patients during previous years to build a comorbidity index or the secondary diagnoses. For the latter, we revert to causes-of-death registry data on the regional level (ISTAT).

Expected Results: We expect a positive relationship between changes in travel time on AMI mortality and readmission rates. We also expect to find a positive relationship between the total number of hospitals in a defined radius around the residence of the patient and AMI mortality and readmission rate.

Discussion: Hospital closures, while potentially improving efficiency through economies of scale, could decrease geographical access and therefore increase event-to-treatment time. Our results are crucial given the importance to undertake the steps to ensure geographical access post hospital closures such as improved emergency transportation and increasing the capacity of surrounding hospitals.